

HERMENEUTIC TENDENCIES IN MYSTICAL TEXT ANNOTATIONS: SCHLEIERMACHER'S GRAMMATICAL HERMENEUTICS AND THE OTTOMAN MASNAVI ANNOTATION TRADITION*

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Abstract

The human effort to understand or make sense of any phenomenon or thought has paved the way for the emergence of various explanation and interpretation activities throughout history. Theological hermeneutics, which emerged in the Jewish and Christian religions to ensure the Holy Book was correctly understood by its recipients, has its counterpart in the Islamic world as Tafsir, Ta'wil, and Annotation. Theological hermeneutics, which developed from an understanding based on the explanation and interpretation of sacred texts, utilized allegorical and literal interpretation styles, while annotators, especially those explaining Sufi texts, preferred an exoteric and esoteric understanding of explanation. Many Sufi works, which are considered classics in the Islamic world and are generally written in verse, have been explained within the Ottoman annotation tradition. Rumi's *Masnavi*, in particular, with its layers of Sufism-based wisdom in terms of meaning, has been annotated by different scholars since the 15th century. In a significant part of these annotations, it is seen that the annotation method adopted by the annotators resembles the grammatical method used by Friedrich Schleiermacher, one of the important hermeneutics of the 19th century and the founder of modern hermeneutics, in his textual interpretations. In this study, we will first provide information about Schleiermacher's hermeneutics; then, we will emphasize the aspects of the *Masnavi* annotators that overlap with Schleiermacher's grammatical method during their annotation process.

Keywords: Annotation, Hermeneutics, Masnavi Annotations, Schleiermacher Hermeneutics, Grammatical Method.

Introduction

Throughout human history, one of the most important issues that societies have frequently focused on is the effort to make sense of events and phenomena that occur outside of themselves. Although this effort cannot be determined on a biological level, its existence in human codes of creation is an indisputable reality from a mental perspective. In the past, whether it was the meaning of a natural event whose cause people did not know, or a written text that shaped social life, it took its place in their world of thought as a question mark whose cause needed to be understood.

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A number of different approaches that deal with the problem of understanding or interpreting what is read have emerged precisely from this need: the attempt to understand the incomprehensible, and its natural consequence, the instinct to disseminate what is understood (Toprak, 2003: 7). These approaches include hermeneutics, whose origins are based on the understanding and interpretation of Homer's works and which deeply influenced the Christian religion, as well as exegesis and annotation, which involve the explanation of the verses in the Quran. The most important common aspect of these two approaches, which undertake the mission of explaining and interpreting religious texts in particular, is their belief that the texts they are based on have an inherently complex structure that is difficult to understand. Viewed from this perspective, the work performed by the annotator and the hermeneuticist in terms of better understanding or avoiding misunderstanding the text is actually similar in terms of its main lines. These two disciplines of interpretation, operating within different religious and cultural values, often adopt a similar and sometimes identical approach while explaining the text.

Understanding itself is a natural state, and the need for hermeneutics only arises if understanding does not occur naturally (Bilen, 2022: 71). On the other hand, the aim in annotation is to eliminate ambiguity and reveal what is hidden (Saraç, 2010: 121). In other words, it is, in a sense, an attempt to make the text at hand understandable. The most important indicator of this situation is that the root words of both interpretative approaches carry meanings such as “explanation, explication, translation, exposure, and interpretation.” The activity of trying to make sense of the unknown essentially consists of two essential elements in the analysis of written texts. The first of these is understanding, and the second is interpretation. As a natural result of the mental flow, the first step in explaining a written text is to understand that text. Failure to understand the current text completely or sufficiently will cause the interpretation to be flawed, incomplete, or incorrect in various respects. Therefore, the common ground in the emergence of commentaries—which include the hermeneutic interpretation of religious texts and the explanation of religious-Sufistic works in Islamic culture—is the claim to better understand the text. The basic basis of this claim is that the reader, who is the recipient of the text, does not have sufficient knowledge to comprehend some of the concepts in the narrative patterns.

Within the semantic world of Classical Turkish Literature, it is frequently encountered to annotate some works—such as the *Masnavi*, *Gulistân*, *Bahâristân*, *Gulşen-i Râz*, etc.—that were generally written in Persian, are considered classics, and whose general framework is determined by Sufism. The most important reason for the large number of annotations on such works is that Sufism and religious orders had a wide following in the social structure of Anatolia. In fact, Ahmed Eflâkî's biographical work, *Menâkibü'l-'arifîn*, cites Hüsameddin Çelebi as the source, who stated that Rumi wrote the *Masnavi* to explain the Quran and to help ascetics who entered the path of the order find the right way. Of course, the recipients of the *Masnavi* were not limited to ascetics alone; it also had a deep impact on large communities of people. The main purpose of such works, which aim to convey religion and mysticism—the fundamental dynamics of society—to people in the most effective way, is not to demonstrate artistic skill but to ensure that the message reaches its intended audience by using the power of art. On the one hand, the poetic prowess of the authors who wrote these works, and on the other hand, the aesthetic pleasure that mystical wisdom reaches through poetry, have been praised by the masses. At this point, the annotators who came into play initiated annotation activities, to the extent of their own possibilities and abilities, in order for people to better understand the aforementioned classical works.

The *Masnavi*, one of the most frequently annotated works in the Sufi annotation literature, was first annotated in verse by Mu'înî bin Mustafa in 1436 under the title *Masnavi-i Murâdiyye* for the Ottoman ruler of the period. Since this first annotation of the *Masnavi*, multiple annotations, in verse or prose, have been produced in almost every century.

The *Masnavi*, which has an annotation tradition spanning approximately six hundred years, features a similar methodology that annotators follow while interpreting the couplets. Tunca Kortantamer describes the methodological stages followed by the *Masnavi* annotators as follows:

“In this type of annotation, the text is given first. Then, words and concepts are often explained in a long or short way, depending on the nature of the annotation, mostly focusing on grammar. The world of meaning hidden in them is then sought to be revealed. If there are ideas that have been put forward on this subject before, they are mentioned and preferences are made. The world of allusions is explained. The annotations of Sa’dî, Hâfîz, and the Masnavi are generally like this.” (Kortantamer, 1994: 2-3).

In these statements by Tunca Kortantamer, where he explains the stages of a classical annotation, the phrase “the hidden world of meaning in words and concepts” is especially important because it symbolizes the layers of meaning contained within Sufi annotation texts. When we look at the explanations and interpretations made by the *Masnavi* annotators at the word and sentence level, we see that they mention a two- or even three-layered meaning when explaining some couplets. Viewed from this perspective, it also becomes clear why Sufi poets such as Rumi, Sena’i, and Attar preferred to use poetry while revealing their intellectual worlds. As Andrews puts it, the symbols in religious texts change their qualities within the poem, but such a change does not make the symbols meaningless; rather, it lends them more meaning (Andrews, 2001: 83).

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We can see a similar analysis of the layers of meaning found at both word and sentence levels during the explanation of the couplets by the *Masnavi* annotators in the interpretations of the Holy Bible by Christian and Jewish theologian hermeneuticists. The basis of the interpretations of the Old and New Testament texts by the Jewish hermeneuticist Philo and the Christian theologian Origen, who were among the first commentators of the Holy Bible, was the allegorical and grammatical (literal) interpretation method. While allegorical interpretation attempts to reach the hidden meaning of a text with the help of an interpretative key external to the text, the grammatical interpretation of a text seeks to reach its meaning by examining the linguistic tools and relations within it (Jeanrond, 2007: 44). In a sense, the exoteric meaning used by annotators in our classical annotation culture corresponds to the grammatical interpretation, while the esoteric explanation corresponds to the allegorical interpretation. The form of expression that theological hermeneutics describes as allegorical interpretation and is generally expressed with symbols is found in a significant part of Sufi poems. The “ney” (reed flute) used in the first couplets of the *Masnavi*, and which is one of the basic metaphors of not only Turkish but also Iranian, Urdu, and Indian Sufi poetry, is one of the words used as a Sufi symbol in the poems of many Sufi poets, especially Senâ’î. When the *Masnavi* annotators mention the “ney,” they explain it in terms of form (exoteric) and meaning (esoteric), as expressed by Rumi. Mustafa Şem’î, one of the 16th-century annotators, states that what is meant by the “ney” in the first couplet of the *Masnavi* is “murshid-i kamil” (the perfect guide) (Dağlar, 2009: 218). Ahmed Avni Konuk, one of the 20th-century *Masnavi* annotators, says that the primary intention is the exoteric meaning, due to the sorrowful sound of the “ney,” but the real intention is the “murshid-i kamil,” which is Rumi himself (Tahrâlî, Eraydın, 2011: 71).

It is quite natural to see certain aspects of this style of interpretation in theological hermeneutics reflected in the *Masnavi* annotations. After all, the main purpose of both explanatory and interpretive frameworks is to convey the meanings of the text they are based on to the recipient in all its aspects. Therefore, it is quite natural to use similar techniques and methods that overlap with each other in various ways during this transmission. On the other hand, the interpretive techniques of theological hermeneutics, the foundations of which were laid by Philo but systematized by Origen, were used in Christian theology's attempts to make sense of the Holy Bible until Martin Luther. Martin Luther, the founder of the Protestant denomination, began his radical change in the principles of Christian belief by rejecting previous interpretations of the Bible and adopting an interpretation based on the principle of explaining the Bible with the Bible (*sola scriptura*). Following Luther came Friedrich Schleiermacher, another Christian theologian who is considered the founder of modern hermeneutics. Schleiermacher is remembered as the initiator of modern hermeneutics in history because, unlike all these theorists with a theological background, he did not limit his method to interpreting and understanding sacred texts. Instead, he started from a general hermeneutics that encompassed all areas—not only written texts but also speech (Toprak, 2003: 79).

Schleiermacher, while interpreting various texts belonging to different branches of science, discusses a hermeneutic approach that can be valid for every text instead of methods and techniques determined specifically for each one. In other words, instead of creating a special hermeneutic approach for each theological, legal, or philological text, he attempts to create a general hermeneutics that can be valid for all of them. This new interpretation approach, also called Romantic hermeneutics, has two basic explanatory methods: the grammatical and the psychological (or technical). The grammatical method, in its simplest definition, is the interpretation of a text based on language and within the possibilities of language. Considering that text annotation is also essentially a philological activity, it is clear that the grammatical method—one of the interpretation techniques of Schleiermacher's hermeneutics—resembles annotation in some ways. In this study, we will first provide information about Schleiermacher's hermeneutics and the grammatical method, which is one of his interpretation techniques. Then, we will emphasize the similarities between the grammatical method and the annotation approach applied by Mustafa Şem'î (16th century), İsmail Rusûhî (17th century), İsmail Bursevî (18th century), and Ahmed Avni Konuk (20th century) to the first two couplets of the *Masnavi* in their annotations. By comparing Schleiermacher's modern hermeneutics with a non-Western intellectual tradition (Ottoman *Masnavi* Commentaries), this study argues that the effort for 'grammatical understanding' is a global hermeneutic universal. "This discovery expands the history of Western-centered hermeneutics and adds a new dimension to the historical continuity of philological approaches."

1. The Nature of Understanding: Schleiermacher's Hermeneutics

Friedrich Schleiermacher was a versatile reformist theologian who lived between 1768 and 1834. Schleiermacher, who had works on topics that shaped the intellectual dynamics of society—especially hermeneutics, as well as philology, philosophy, pedagogy, and theology—holds a distinctive position in the history of hermeneutics. In Gadamer's words, until that time, theologians and philologists had only used hermeneutics as a tool to reveal the dogmatic meaning of the text, but with Schleiermacher, the path to historicism was opened (Gadamer, 1995: 15). Between 1810 and 1834, he served as the Chair of Protestant Theology at the University of Berlin, where he taught hermeneutics. After his death, his student F. Lücke published the book *Hermeneutics and Criticism* (*Hermeneutik und Kritik*) in 1838, which reflects the essence of his views on hermeneutics and includes his works from after 1819. Due to his affiliation with a world of thought rooted in theology, his first writings include criticisms of the philosophical views of figures such as Kant, Spinoza, and Jacobi on topics like being and ethics.

Rejecting Kant's views on the soul and God, Schleiermacher supports Spinoza's understanding of monism, especially in his two essays titled *On Freedom* and *On What Gives Value to Life* (Forster, 2022: 1).

After moving to Berlin, Schleiermacher met Friedrich Schlegel, one of the important representatives of Romanticism, and this deeply influenced his views on the philosophy of religion. In 1799, he outlined his views on the philosophy of religion in his first and most important work, *On Religion*, and thus gained great fame. According to Andrew Bowie, who edited and translated his work *Hermeneutics and Criticism* from German to English, this work, which emerged at the instigation of the Romantics of the period—especially Friedrich Schlegel—also launched Schleiermacher into the intellectual arena (Schleiermacher, 1998: XII). Schleiermacher, whose life in Berlin ended for various reasons, began teaching at Halle University in 1804. The author, who began giving courses on ethics in 1804–05, also started giving his famous and important courses on hermeneutics during this period (Forster, 2022: 3). Kurt Mueller-Vollmer states that Schleiermacher's interest in hermeneutic problems actually began in Berlin in 1796, when he was with Friedrich Schlegel and other Romantics, and that he became the founder of modern hermeneutics thanks to the traces he received from Schlegel's thought-provoking insights (Schleiermacher, 2006: 72). The main point that the sources providing information about Schleiermacher's life and works agree on is that he is the founder of modern hermeneutics. The general framework of Schleiermacher's hermeneutics, whose main dynamics are formed by understanding and interpreting, can be explained as follows, again based on his works:

This well-articulated claim, which Schleiermacher used in the introduction of his 1819 lecture on hermeneutics, describes his main orientation in a single sentence: To determine the boundaries of a general hermeneutics as the art of understanding (Palmer, 2008: 121). Indeed, in the introduction of Schleiermacher's work *Hermeneutics and Criticism*, where he explains his views on hermeneutics, the author's statement, "There is currently no general hermeneutics as the art of understanding; there are only many special hermeneutics" (Schleiermacher, 1998: 73), serves as a criticism of special hermeneutics, which, until then, had tried to solve specific texts (religion, law, philology, etc.) with their own rules. Hermeneutics, which was only an interpretive activity until the 19th century, became generalized as the "science of understanding" with Schleiermacher.

Although a theologian, Schleiermacher, unlike the theorists of theological origin who had attempted to interpret sacred texts with hermeneutics before him, opposed the distinction between sacred and secular texts with the method he developed. According to Schleiermacher, if a sacred text needs to be subjected to a different method of interpretation to be better understood, this need arises spontaneously during the exegesis process (Toprak, 2003: 40). There are undoubtedly differences between these different types of texts, and for this reason, each discipline develops theoretical tools for its own specific problems; but there is a more fundamental unity underlying all these differences (Palmer, 2008: 121). In other words, when starting to analyze an existing religious and philological text, the procedure to be applied for both should be the same. Of course, these branches of science have their own rules and principles. However, during the exegesis process, issues that will facilitate the understanding of the existing text should be highlighted.

Schleiermacher, who calls hermeneutics the art of understanding, focuses on three main points during his text analysis technique: speaking, interpreting, and understanding activities. Unlike the traditional understanding of hermeneutics, Schleiermacher, although he gives priority to the activity of "understanding," does not separate it from interpretation. This is because, according to him, the two are completely interconnected: every understanding is also an interpretation, and likewise, every interpretation indicates an understanding. In performing this, the interpreter transforms a foreign text into their own language by using its concepts (Joachim, 1995: 329). If hermeneutics is not limited to explaining the different practical problems that arise when interpreting different types of texts, then it can take the act of understanding as a starting point. According to Schleiermacher, hermeneutics is literally "the art of understanding" (Palmer, 2008: 123).

On the other hand, Schleiermacher sought to go beyond the classical understanding—which reduces the activities of understanding and interpretation solely to the explanation of written texts—and adapt it to speech, which is the basis of communication between people. This is because, according to Schleiermacher, speech is the tool of the social nature of thought, and this explains the mutual relationship between rhetoric and the science of interpretation, as well as their common connection with dialectics.

According to Schleiermacher, the hermeneutic process consists of the following three stages:

- Correct expression of thoughts
- Correct understanding of thoughts
- Transfer of understood thoughts (Taşdelen, 2007: 191)

While trying to explain a literary text, Schleiermacher starts by determining the linguistic and historical nature of the text before applying his methodology to it. Especially if the current text is an old text written in a different language, as in the annotations we are discussing, the first action the hermeneuticist must take is to eliminate the linguistic and historical obstacles related to the text. Schleiermacher, who starts the interpretive activity only after these stages, defines the purpose of hermeneutics as the historical and intuitive, subjective and objective reconstruction of a word and establishes some rules for this purpose (Schleiermacher, 1911: 147). These concepts, which Schleiermacher described as historical and intuitive, subjective and objective, would also form the basis of the grammatical and psychological (technical) analysis techniques he would later develop. According to Schleiermacher, to prevent misunderstandings in the analysis of a literary text, it is necessary to first reach the level of the author of the text in subjective and objective terms. While objective accessibility includes the basic characteristics of the language used by the author in the text, the subjective quality is related to the details of his life. Of course, when the subject is the language used by the author and information about his biography, it is necessary to know the conditions of the period in which he lived.

According to Schleiermacher, when these conditions are met at the beginning, we understand the text as much as the author in the first stage, and in the later process, we understand the text even better than the author (Schleiermacher, 1911: 146). Schleiermacher describes this process as “restructuring” and attributes it to two criteria. The objective criterion aims to reveal the attitude of the word within the speech and the information within the speech as a product of the language. The subjective criterion, on the other hand, is the one by which the interpreter reveals the author's personality and then intuitively tries to understand the impact of the text on its author (Toprak, 2003: 42–43). After this entire preparatory phase is completed, grammatical and psychological (technical) analysis methods are used to explain each section of the text. Schleiermacher, who maintains an equal distance from both interpretation techniques when explaining a literary text or speech, generally recommends starting the interpretation with the grammatical method.

2. Schleiermacher's Grammatical Method in Turkish Masnavi Annotations

Throughout human history, religious texts in particular—which shaped social and individual life and generally required explanation—were attempted to be conveyed to society by the intellectuals of the time using various methods of explanation. Historically, the interpretation activities initiated in ancient Greece to better understand the texts in Homer's works, the *Iliad* and the *Odyssey*, also constitute the foundations of hermeneutics. The interpretation activities conducted in the early period, which generally included cultural elements, were later used by Jewish and Christian clergymen under the name of theological hermeneutics. Early hermeneuticists utilized two methods while explaining texts: literal (grammatical) and allegorical interpretation. While allegorical interpretation attempts to reach the hidden meaning of a text with the help of an interpretative key external to the text, the grammatical interpretation of a text seeks to reach its meaning by examining the linguistic tools and relations within it (Jeanrond, 2007: 44).

This approach has traveled from ancient times to medieval Europe—especially in Luther’s interpretations of the holy books—and from there to Schleiermacher, the founder of modern hermeneutics. Since Schleiermacher, there have been serious changes both in the general understanding of hermeneutics and in the content of analysis techniques. However, it is certain that the basis of the grammatical interpretation understanding of both Schleiermacher and the hermeneuticists before him is language, and in particular, the semantic dimension of words and grammatical rules.

Schleiermacher puts a text through certain filters while analyzing it with the grammatical analysis method. First of all, according to Schleiermacher, the words used in the text do not possess a single meaning by nature. In both literary texts and colloquial language, the words used by the subject who is the source of the expression have a flexible structure in terms of the meaning they contain. Therefore, words, which are the basic building blocks of language, have changed both in form and meaning throughout the historical process in which they were used. According to Schleiermacher, a word with a single meaning would not require a grammar, and a dictionary alone would be sufficient to learn the language to which that word belongs. This is because it should not be forgotten that the sentence is the most important factor that organizes the algorithms of words within the language. Since the grammatical method must first reveal the historical structures of the language, grammar, sentence structure, and semantics, it adopts a historicist approach. With the help of the data obtained in light of this historical approach, it becomes more clearly understood in the later stages, especially how the author individually presents the language.

Schleiermacher’s understanding of word-focused analysis in grammatical interpretation is based on two principles. The first of these is to select words one by one and to reveal the semantic aspect of the word, on the one hand, and the formal aspect of the word, on the other. The second principle is to start with a single word and examine the word's situation first within the sentence in which it is used and then within the entire text where that sentence is found. This is because, according to Schleiermacher, a complete understanding can only be achieved through connections established with contexts that start from the smallest unit and gradually expand (Toprak, 2003: 45). Schleiermacher’s approach to words is reminiscent of the inductive method in philosophy. The hermeneuticist attempts to reveal the author’s intention in a general expression by starting from parts such as words, sentences, and textual explanations in literary text analysis.

One of the indispensable conditions of Schleiermacher’s grammatical interpretation method is that the hermeneuticist should be interested in the content of the text he is working on and should know the language of that text very well. In fact, we can find similar themes of this approach in Luther’s understanding of interpreting the holy book, though he lived much earlier than Schleiermacher. Luther argues that to properly interpret the Bible, the languages in which it was first written—Latin and Greek—should be known very well. According to Schleiermacher, in addition to being proficient in the language of the text he is working on, the hermeneuticist should also have a good knowledge of the vocabulary of the field in which the text was written. Schleiermacher, who gives the Bible as an example, emphasizes that a hermeneuticist who aspires to interpret the Bible text should have extensive knowledge, especially about Christianity. This is because the nature of this hermeneutics understanding requires that the hermeneuticist coincide with the intellectual world of the author of the text, both linguistically and intellectually.

Of course, when the subject is religion—which especially has the power to shape all layers of social life and makes the masses run after it—it is obvious that the words spoken in daily language or mere dictionaries will not be sufficient for explanation in the solution of a religious text. This is because words, which are the reflection of thought in concrete life, often undergo an expansion of meaning according to the requirements and needs of the scientific field in which they are used and can be used outside of their meanings in the dictionary.

In fact, the biggest reason for the emergence of terminological dictionaries specific to scientific fields such as philosophy, literature, sociology, mysticism, etc. in the history of science is that words often shed their real meanings and take on a technical meaning. Schleiermacher also recommends that the hermeneuticist refer to dictionaries and grammar books when he cannot solve the literary text he is working on despite having sufficient knowledge.

Schleiermacher's final suggestion regarding textual interpretation is the understanding of benefiting from parallel works. In other words, if the hermeneuticist has any doubts or hesitations regarding the main idea of the text after applying the principles explained above, he should refer to different works of the same author or other works written in a similar vein. The approach of utilizing a different work of the author or another work that deals with a subject parallel to the text at hand actually provides the hermeneuticist who performs the interpretive activity with two benefits:

- The opportunity to test the accuracy of the interpretation that the hermeneuticist has shaped in his world of thought.
- The opportunity to gain new ideas about the secondary concepts that will enable the main idea to emerge.

There are many examples supporting this approach of Schleiermacher in the tradition of annotation, which holds a considerable volume in the cultural life of the Ottomans, and especially in Sufi annotations, including the commentaries on the *Masnavi*.

In Turkish literature, a significant portion of the Sufi texts annotated on, especially during the Ottoman period, were written in verse. On the one hand, the terminology and philosophical tenets specific to Sufism—which is called the mystical dimension of Islam—and on the other hand, the immense expressive power of poetry chosen as a medium to convey this systematic thought, have made the existing texts difficult to understand. Annemarie Schimmel has beautifully summarized the problem of understanding that arises when religion, and especially Sufism, conveys its values of belief through poetry with the following statement: "Because poetry offers almost unlimited possibilities for creating new relationships between worldly and otherworldly images, religious and worldly ideas; a talented poet can achieve a perfect interaction of both levels and make even the most worldly poem carry a distinctly religious flavor" (Schimmel, 1975: 288).

The fact that the Sufis who grew up both in Iran and in the Seljuk and Ottoman lands (Rumi, Attar, Molla Cami, Şebüsteri) wrote their works—which could be described as classics—in poetry because they were powerful poets prepared the ground for the writing of annotations that would explain these texts. Rumi, one of the most important representatives of Sufism that flourished in Anatolia, and his *Masnavi*, which he wrote in Persian, are among the rare works that explain all aspects of Sufi etiquette in verse. After the *Masnavi* was written, both religious circles, state administrators, and members of the public who tried to be inspired by its spirit translated or annotated it many times. Following the annotation called *Masnavi-i Murâdiyye*, which was written by Mu'inî at the request of Murat II in 1436 and was the translation and annotation of the first volume of the *Masnavi*, the tradition of annotating the *Masnavi* began, and this tradition continues today. Now let us see how the issues specific to Schleiermacher's grammatical analysis method mentioned above are applied to the first two couplets in the *Masnavi* annotations of Mustafa Şem'î (16th century), İsmail Rusûhî (17th century), İsmail Bursevî (18th century), and Ahmed Avni Konuk (20th century).

2.1. Polysemy in Words

The first point Schleiermacher mentions in his grammatical interpretation technique is his view that words do not have a single meaning. Schleiermacher, who even makes a distinction between prose and poetry during text analysis, says that poetry is a more difficult text to interpret. If it is a poem that is being studied, the basic element that needs to be taken into consideration is that this type of literature often deliberately and willingly prefers polysemy.

Therefore, the subordinate thoughts it contains are in the majority, and each element in the text usually has a special meaning (Toprak, 2003: 47). It would not be wrong to say that Rumi is a powerful poet who wrote his work in verse and that he used all the power of poetry to express his views in his work. It is not overlooked that Rumi is especially careful to use some words with more than one meaning in the *Masnavi*, which is one of the best examples of the transfer of Sufi rules through the art of poetry. Indeed, it is possible to see the existence of this situation in the allegorical approach of Origen, one of the founders of theological hermeneutics. Origen also divides the words that play a key role in religious texts into three layers in terms of the meaning they contain, and calls them body, soul, and spirit, respectively. While annotating the first two couplets of the *Masnavi*, the *Masnavi* annotators make semantic expansions of some words that they believe are the starting point of the couplet. This approach, which is called the exoteric and esoteric meaning in Sufi terminology, shows a serious similarity to Schleiermacher's understanding of polysemy in word.

Ahmed Avni Konuk, one of the 20th-century *Masnavi* annotators, divides the meanings of the ney (reed flute)—one of the basic words of the first couplet—into semantic layers as exoteric and esoteric. He even divides the esoteric meaning expressed by the word into two parts. According to Konuk, the ney evokes a feeling of pity in the hearts of listeners due to the bitterness of the sound it makes in its exoteric meaning. “It is permissible to use the term *ney* to refer to the apparent ney. Because the sound of the ney is more powerful than the sound of any other instrument, it brings compassion to the hearts of those who listen and brings people to ecstasy.” (Tahralı, Eraydın, 2011: 78). Another aspect of the ney emphasized by the annotator in terms of its apparent meaning is its seven holes. It is stated that these holes correspond to the seven limbs of a person. “The seven holes of the ney are a sign of the seven external limbs of a person, and human actions emerge from these limbs.” (Tahralı, Eraydın, 2011: 78).

Konuk, who explains the exoteric aspects of the word, then goes on to explain the esoteric meanings. According to him, what is meant by the ney is Rumi himself and, consequently, the murshid-i kamil (the perfect guide). “Rumi refers to his own honorable body with the expression 'Listen to this ney.' This is because the ney is hollow, and the breath of the person who blows it produces sound from it. The body of the murshid-i kamil is similar to the ney.” (Tahralı, Eraydın, 2011: 78). Of course, this ney is not a murshid-i kamil before being plucked from the *neyistân* (reed-bed). After being plucked from the *neyistân*, it is essential for it to be leveled (or refined) by a perfect master in order to become a *murshid-i kamil*. Otherwise, it will be a ney that does not produce beautiful melodies because its interior has not been leveled throughout its life; that is, it will be an imperfect man.

“For example, a murshid-i kamil (the perfect guide) is like a “ney” (reed flute) that is cut from a reed bed and is suitable for the ney player to blow and produce beautiful melodies. An imperfect man is like a “ney” that, although cut from a reed bed, has not been leveled and is not suitable for producing beautiful melodies and sounds because of its fullness. If this ney is also leveled by a perfect master and its interior is emptied, it becomes a beautiful ney.” (Tahralı, Eraydın, 2011: 78).

2.2. The Inductive Method (Part-Whole Relationship)

The second principle that Schleiermacher applied in the grammatical analysis method is the approach of revealing the main idea of the text based on the meanings of certain words in the text, which we can also call the inductive method. For example, a complete sentence is a unity; we understand the meaning of a single word by looking at its place in the whole sentence, while, on the other hand, the meaning of the sentence as a whole is based on individual words (Palmer, 2008: 124). In fact, this approach of Schleiermacher, who tried to apply the relationship between the part and the whole at the word level, was used by Martin Luther in the Middle Ages under the title of the “hermeneutic circle” in order to interpret the biblical texts.

Accordingly, in this two-way interaction between the part and the whole, each side contributes to the other in a cyclical and reciprocal direction. The understanding of finding the main idea of a literary text based on the part-whole relationship at the word level is also present in the approaches of the *Masnavi* annotators. The method that Şem'î, a 16th-century commentator, applied in order to obtain the meaning while commenting on the second couplet of the *Masnavi* is exactly this type. Şem'î chose the words “neyistân, merd u zen” in the couplet “K'ezneyistân tâ merâ bü'brîdeend, Eznefirem merd ü zen nâlîdeend” (Since they cut me from the reeds / Men and women moan from my cry) and “cudâyîhâ” (separations) in the first couplet as steps in order to reveal the meaning of the couplet. Şem'î, who emphasized the terminological meanings of the selected parts rather than their literal meanings, concluded the basic meaning he obtained after combining these parts with the expression “result of meaning” (*netîce-i ma'nâ*), which is a common usage in the Ottoman annotation tradition. The quote supporting Şem'î's inductive analysis reads:

“Men and women groaned from my wailing and wailing. What is meant by neyistan is the first level, the second level, the third level, and the fourth level (of being). The word cudâyîhâ is used in plural form. What is meant by men and women is the people. What is meant by man is the mind and what is meant by woman is the soul. Result of meaning (Netîce-i ma'nâ): It indicates the necessity of wailing and wailing due to the separation of the eternal beloved and the original homeland.” (Dağlar, 2009: 219).

2.3. Competence in Language and Terminology

Another principle of Schleiermacher regarding grammatical analysis is that the hermeneuticist who performs the analysis should be interested in the text, have a command of its language, and especially possess knowledge of the terminology of the field in which the text was written. When the literary text to be analyzed is the *Masnavi*, and the language in which it was written is Persian and partly Arabic, the annotator needs to know both languages with all their nuances. The necessity for the annotators to know these two languages arises not only from the translation of the *Masnavi* text but also from the fact that the sources to be consulted during the annotation (especially the Quran, hadith, and Sufism sources) are written in these two languages. As is known, one of the most important reasons why Rumi wrote the *Masnavi* was to teach the disciples the methods and requirements of Sufism, as stated in *Menakib-ı Sipehsalar*. Therefore, the annotators who comment on the *Masnavi* must naturally have a good knowledge of the Quran and hadith literature, along with a strong command of Sufi terminology. When we look at the biographies of the four annotators we have studied, we see that all of them are members of religious orders.

In addition to their membership in religious orders, the fact that these annotators received their education on Sufism, religion, and Arabic-Persian from the lodges—that is, they learned the work from the source—provided them with a great advantage in terms of the interest, language, and terminological knowledge that Schleiermacher mentioned. One of the clearest examples of the annotators' accumulation of knowledge regarding the literary language and terminology of the text is undoubtedly the quality of the other works they have written. Ismail Hakkı Bursevî is at the forefront of these annotators. The annotator, who has more than 100 works ranging from Quran exegesis to hadith and Sufi works annotation, requires a serious knowledge of Arabic-Persian for the works he works on. In the annotation of the annotator, we can easily see his mastery of language and terminology in *Rûhu'l-Masnavi*, where he commented on the *Masnavi*. In this work, Bursevî includes a total of 23 features, including religious, mystical, and linguistic features, regarding the meaning of the first letter “bâ” (in *Bishnev*), which begins the *Masnavi*. The quote detailing Bursevî's analysis of the letter “Bâ” (*in Bishnev*) reads as follows:

“What is known from now on is that there are many aspects of starting the Masnavi with the letter “Bâ”. One reason for this is that the Bismillah starts with this letter. And another reason is that it points to the beginning, and that this beginning is the Masnavi. And even one of them is a sign of the emergence of existence, that the human being is in the form of the letter Alif in this creation.

And one of them is that the dot of unity in the letter “Bā” indicates the emergence of the first being, from which the secret of person emerges. And another reason is that the letter “Bā” is used for affixation in Arabic and Persian. And one of the reasons is the letter “Bā” that a person uses when he first acquires a mouth in the spirit world and begins to speak. And one of the reasons is that the letter “Bā” refers to Balkh, the city where Rumi was born.” (Güleç, 2002: 2-3-4-5-6).

The most prominent scholarly feature displayed by the annotators in their *Masnavi* commentaries, especially Ismail Hakkı Bursevî and İsmail Rusûhî, is their mastery of Arabic and Persian. When analyzing the couplets they address, particularly in terms of meaning and grammar, a significant majority of the sources they cite as references are works written in Arabic or Persian. The fact that they make references to these works from various perspectives based on their original languages is important in demonstrating the annotators’ proficiency in Arabic and Persian. In this respect, it is noteworthy that İsmail Rusûhî, in his commentary, provides information compiled from many Islamic scholars, especially verses (of the Quran) and hadith, in Arabic, and subsequently offers their explanations. The annotator refers to Qadi Baydawi’s commentary, written in Arabic, to state that the expressions “merd ü zen” (man and woman) in the second couplet of the *Masnavi* are interpreted by some exegetes as earth and sky.

“And these sky and earth are likened by the rhetoricians (fusehâ) and exegetes (müfessirîn) to man and woman, as Baydawi said in his Tafsir: And We sent down from the heaven water, and brought forth thereby from the fruits a provision for you. And even though the coming forth of the fruits is by the power and will of God, He made the water mixed with the soil a cause for their coming forth and a material for them, like the semen for the animal, or He created (them) in the descending water.” (Tanyıldız, 2010: 211).

2.4. Reference to Parallel Sources

The last principle that Schleiermacher suggested for text analysis with the grammatical method is the reference to other works of the author of the text or to parallel works written on the same subject. In Turkish *Masnavi* annotations, annotators referred to a wide range of sources for couplets they had difficulty in explaining or were unsure of their meaning:

- Rumi's own works
- Works of different authors
- The annotator's own works

It’s possible to divide these reference materials into two groups:

1. Meaning (Content) Sources: Sources that explain the meaning of the text (religious, mystical, historical, philosophical, etc.).
2. Form (Linguistic) Sources: Sources that explain the language of the text (grammar books and dictionaries).

The Quran and Hadiths are the sources that annotators refer to most during their annotations. Apart from these, it is seen that they also referred to works written by great Sufis, dictionary and grammar books, and works on Islamic sciences (tafsir, fiqh, theology, creed, etc.). As a matter of fact, Rumi’s own works are among the sources frequently consulted and referenced by annotators. The observation of Amil Çelebioğlu, who has important works on the *Masnavi*, is a very appropriate approach: "It is possible to say that Rumi can be understood better and more accurately, and also that the accuracy of the old annotators can be better understood, if he can be commented on in a completely systematic and comparative manner, primarily with his own works (Çelebioğlu, 1983: 22)."

Ahmed Avni Konuk is one of the annotators who frequently refers to Rumi’s own works in his annotation. After presenting his own opinion, especially on Sufi topics, Konuk refers to another work of Rumi in order to establish this on a more solid basis. Konuk’s quote regarding the meaning of the ney’s "moaning" (as the words of the perfect human being) and his use of Rumi’s parallel work reads:

“What is meant by moaning is the words of the perfect human being about the facts and information that he declares in front of wise and ignorant people, and this consists of similar moans of Rumi from the beginning to the end of the Masnavi-i Sharif, and all classes of people who listen to Rumi's words are very impressed by those high meanings. As a matter of fact, in the 24th chapter of his book Fihi Mâ Fih, he says: ‘One day I was preaching among a crowd. There was a group of infidels among them. They cried during my sermon and created joy and mood.’” (Tahralı, Eraydın, 2011: 73).

Ismail Rusûhî, one of the most important annotators of the *Masnavi* and known as the Hazrat-i Sharikh (The Illustrious Commentator), is also one of the annotators who frequently uses sources in his commentary. While commenting on the first couplet of the *Masnavi*, he refers to many sources such as verses (of the Quran), hadiths, *tafsir* (exegesis), and the history of the prophets. The main reason for this is to ensure that the subject he explains is fully understood by associating it with religious and mystical knowledge. Rusûhî's reference to Imam Fakhr al-Dîn al-Râzî's work, the *Tafsîr al-Kabîr* (The Great Exegesis), demonstrates this scholarly depth:

“Imam Fakhr al-Dîn al-Râzî expresses this in his work Tafsîr al-Kabîr: As it is known, hearing is superior to seeing. That is why whenever Allah mentions these two in the Holy Quran, He prioritizes hearing over seeing. For example, ‘He (Allah) gave you ears, eyes and hearts so that you may be grateful.’ (Nahl, 78) and ‘He (Allah) hears and sees everything.’ (Isra, 1) In each of them, hearing comes before seeing.” (Tanyıldız, 2010: 3).

Conclusion

Throughout human history, texts that have deeply affected social life and guided humanity have been subject to numerous interpretations, often based on the premise that they were not properly understood. These interpretative approaches, which emerged in different forms in Eastern and Western cultures, developed their own methods and techniques based on need. In the West, hermeneutics and the literal (grammatical) and allegorical analysis techniques it developed found their counterparts in Muslim geography as *tafsir* (exegesis), *ta'wil* (esoteric interpretation), and annotation. Classical hermeneutics, which began with the explanation of Homer's texts in ancient times, later evolved into theological hermeneutics by Jewish and Christian clergymen. This process continued until Schleiermacher, the founder of modern hermeneutics. With Schleiermacher, the hermeneutic approach that had previously appealed to the specific texts took on a new, generalized form with its own rules. According to Schleiermacher, instead of a special hermeneutics for each field of science, a general hermeneutic understanding should be developed for the interpretation of all different branches of science. While each field certainly has its own rules and principles, the principles of its own originality come to the fore during interpretation. At the basis of Schleiermacher's logic of interpretation lies an approach with general principles and an understanding of penetrating the world of thought of the author of the analyzed text. Schleiermacher's interpretation technique is divided into two parts: the grammatical and the psychological (technical) methods. As its name suggests, the origin of the grammatical method is language and its characteristics.

One of the most important religious and literary accumulations of Ottoman cultural life is undoubtedly annotations. Being at the center of Sufi life and having a great reputation both in the society where it was written and outside its own geography, Rumi's *Masnavi* has been translated and commented on many times since it was written due to its importance. Many individuals from different segments of social life, especially annotators belonging to religious orders, participated in this cultural activity based on their own talents and experiences. Şem'î (16th century), İsmail Rusûhî (17th century), İsmail Hakkı Bursevî (18th century), and Ahmed Avni Konuk (20th century) are important annotators who commented on the *Masnavi*. When we look at the annotations of these commentators, we see that the core principles mentioned in Schleiermacher's grammatical method are also applied in their annotation.

These principles include: Words having more than one meaning (Polysemy), the main idea being reached by starting from the words one by one (Inductive/Part-Whole), the requirement that the vocabulary of the interpreter and the author be aligned (Language and Terminology Competence), and the reference to the works of the author or other authors to establish the analyses on a solid ground (Parallel Sources). The fact that these two understandings overlap in various aspects, even though they belong to different cultures and different centuries, stems from the common motivation of both to reveal a thought or group of thoughts that they believe to be obscured or closed.

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